

Evaluation of Pneumatization Pattern of Sphenoid Sinus on Computed Tomography Scan in an Urban Nigerian Population

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Abstract

Background: The pneumatization pattern of the sphenoid sinus (SS) is highly variable. A good understanding of sphenoid sinus pneumatization is critical for skull base surgeries and functional endoscopic sinus surgery (FESS) in order to avoid serious complications.

Purpose: The purpose of this study is to present the pneumatization pattern of the sphenoid sinus in adult participants in our environment.

Methods: This is a retrospective study conducted at a privately owned Radiodiagnostics Center after obtaining institutional ethical approval. Brain Computed Tomography images of 200 patients aged ≥ 18 years were studied for the variant pneumatization patterns of the sphenoid sinus.

The data obtained were analyzed using the statistical package for social science, IBM SPSS (version 25.0 by incorporation, Chicago - Illinois, USA 2017). The continuous variables will be expressed as means (\bar{x}) and standard deviation (SD). P-value was considered significant at <0.05 . P-value was considered significant at <0.05 .

Results: The majority of the participants were males 118 (59%) with a mean age of 48.3 ± 18.1 years while the female patients were 82(41%) with a mean age of 47.4 ± 17.6 years. The commonest pneumatization pattern is the post sellar type 93(46.5%), followed by the sellar type 53(26.5%) then the presellar type 49(24.5%) and the least common is the conchal type 2(2.5%). None of the pneumatization patterns showed a significant age and gender difference. Sphenoid sinus agenesis was not documented.

Conclusion: The postsellar and conchal type of sphenoid sinus pneumatization was found to be the commonest and the least common in our environment. None of the pneumatization patterns showed a significant age and gender difference. Sphenoid sinus agenesis was not documented.

More Information

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Introduction

The sphenoid sinus (SS) is a mucosa-lined osseous cavity which is separated by a bony septum, which is housed within the body of the sphenoid bone. It communicates with the roof of the nasal cavity through the sphenoidal recess in its anterior wall [22]. Occasionally, it extends laterally into the greater and lesser wings and pterygoid plates of the sphenoid bone and posteriorly to the clivus. Its size varies with an average of 6-7.5 mL [1-4].

The assessment of the anatomical variants of sphenoid bone and sphenoid sinuses has been shown over time to be of great importance in different fields of clinical anatomy. The sphenoid sinuses are considered the most variable structures in the human body and their degree of pneumatization is highly variable and reaches its mature size by 14 years of age [4,22].

Many literature sources attribute the variability of sphenoid sinus pneumatization to differences in imaging techniques, geographical, genetic, and environmental factors.

The SS is classified based on the pattern of pneumatization into conchal, presellar, sellar, and postsellar [23]. In conchal type, the region below the sellar is completely ossified and consists of a solid block of bone with no air cavity. In the presellar type, the air cavity does not penetrate beyond a vertical plane parallel to the anterior sellar wall [23]. In the sellar type, the sinus is well developed, and pneumatization extends beyond the tuberculum sella below the sella and sometimes with bulging of the sellar floor into the sinus cavity. In the postsellar type, the air cavity extends into the body of the sphenoid, continues beyond the posterior margin [5,23].

Globally, the imaging modalities used in the evaluation of the SS are computed tomography (CT), conventional radiography and magnetic resonance imaging (MRI). MRI has a higher soft-tissue resolution but provides less information about bony structures which are conventionally used as anatomic landmarks to guide endoscopic surgery [23]. For this reason, computed tomography scan and conventional radiography are preferred for detecting and delineating the bony landmarks and anatomic variants that facilitate safe

access into the SS for the surgeon with the CT more preferred due to its multiplanar effect [5,23].

Knowing the anatomical details of the sphenoid bone, sphenoid sinus pneumatization patterns and the extent of pneumatization can guide the surgeon through the challenging angles inherent in the approach for functional endoscopic sinus surgery (FESS).

We embarked on this study to ascertain the pattern of SS pneumatization and variations among the genders in our environment.

Materials and Methods

This is a retrospective cross-sectional study of adult patients that had cranial CT for various indications in a Private Radiodiagnostic facility in Jos, North Central Nigeria. We studied the brain CT images, with special focus on the sphenoid bone and sinus of patients with no apparent feature or indication of sinus disease.

Image acquisition was done using a 64-slice CT scanner (Siemens Somatom Sensation) in the axial plane with slice thickness of 2.5 mm and reconstructed at 1.25 mm. Evaluation of the primary axial and reconstructed coronal and sagittal views was done using the bone window. The images were analyzed and the sphenoid sinus pneumatization are then classified into conchal, presellar, sellar and postsellar types.

Data Analysis

The data obtained was analyzed using the statistical package for social science, IBM SPSS (version 25.0 by incorporation, Chicago - Illinois, USA 2017). The continuous variables will be expressed as means (x) and standard deviation (SD). P-value was considered significant at <0.05.

Results

Age and Sex Distribution

The brain CT images of 118 males (59.0%) and 82 females (41.0%) were analyzed in this study. These subjects had an average age of 47.9±17.9years. Higher proportions of both male (22.0%) and female (25.6%) patients were between 41-50 years. Overall mean age of patients was 47.9±17.9 years. Although mean age of male patients was higher (48.3±18.1 years) than female patients (47.4±17.6 years). The difference was not statistically significant (t = 0.748, p = 0.827).

Table 1: Age and Sex Distribution of Patients

Age group (years)	Sex			χ ² /t-test	p-value
	Male	Female	Total		
11-20	9(7.6)	8(9.8)	17(8.5)		
21-30	14(11.9)	9(11.0)	23(11.5)		
31-40	20(16.9)	9(11.0)	29(14.5)		
41-50	26(22.0)	21(25.6)	47(23.5)		
51-60	19(16.1)	15(18.3)	34(17.0)		
61-70	11(9.3)	11(13.4)	22(11.0)		
71-80	17(14.4)	8(9.8)	25(12.5)		

81-90	2(1.7)	1(1.2)	3(1.5)		
Total	118(100.0)	82(100.0)	200(100.0)	3.528	0.832
Mean±SD	48.3±18.1	47.4±17.6	47.9±17.9	0.748	0.827

Sphenoid Sinus Type

Finding on sphenoid sinus type revealed that higher proportion of both male (41.5%) and females (53.7%) had postsellar sphenoid sinus type. Only few male patients (2.5%) and female patients 2.4%) had conchal

sphenoid sinus type. This difference in proportion between male and female gender was not statistically significant ($\chi^2 = 3.830, p = 0.283$) as shown in figure 1 below.

Figure 1: Sphenoid Sinus Type

Table 2: Sphenoid Sinus Type for Age and Sex

Sphenoid Type	Age group (years)	Sex			χ^2	p-value
		Male	Female	Total		
Conchal	11-20	1(3.3)	0(0.0)	1(20.0)	2.903	0.999
	21-30	1(3.3)	0(0.0)	1(20.0)		
	41-50	0(0.0)	1(50.0)	1(20.0)		
	61-70	1(3.3)	1(50.0)	2(40.0)		
	Total	3(100.0)	2(100.0)	5(100.0)		
Presellar	11-20	1(2.9)	0(0.0)	1(20.0)	5.959	0.435
	21-30	6(17.6)	4(26.7)	10(20.4)		
	31-40	8(23.5)	2(13.3)	10(20.4)		
	41-50	5(14.7)	2(13.3)	7(14.3)		
	51-60	4(11.8)	4(26.7)	8(16.3)		
	61-70	4(11.8)	3(20.0)	7(14.3)		
	71-80	6(17.6)	0(0.0)	6(12.2)		
	Total	34(100.0)	15(100.0)	49(100.0)		
Sellar	11-20	5(15.6)	3(14.3)	8(15.1)	4.839	0.733
	21-30	3(9.4)	3(14.3)	6(11.3)		
	31-40	5(15.6)	1(4.8)	6(11.3)		
	41-50	5(15.6)	4(19.0)	9(17.0)		
	51-60	7(21.9)	3(14.3)	10(18.9)		
	61-70	1(3.1)	3(14.3)	4(7.5)		
	71-80	5(15.6)	4(19.0)	9(17.0)		

	81-90	1(3.1)	0(0.0)	1(1.9)		
	Total	32(100.0)	21(100.0)	53(100.0)		
Post-Sellar					2.723	0.946
	11-20	2(4.1)	5(11.4)	7(7.5)		
	21-30	4(8.2)	2(4.5)	6(6.5)		
	31-40	7(14.3)	6(13.6)	13(14.0)		
	41-50	16(32.7)	14(31.8)	30(32.3)		
	51-60	8(16.3)	8(18.2)	16(17.2)		
	61-70	5(10.2)	4(9.1)	9(9.7)		
	71-80	6(12.2)	4(9.1)	10(10.8)		
	81-90	1(2.0)	1(2.3)	2(2.2)		
	Total	49(100.0)	44(100.0)	93(100.0)		

Note: The study showed no significant association between Age and Sex with Sphenoid Sinus Type ($p > 0.05$).

Discussion

A good understanding of sphenoid sinus pneumatization is critical for skull base surgeries and functional endoscopic sinus surgery (FESS) in order to avoid serious complications [24]. For a proper surgical approach, detailed preoperative imaging of the sphenoid sinus and sellar region using radiographic imaging modalities is very necessary.

Our study of two hundred sphenoid sinuses revealed a majority (93, 46.5%) of the patients had postsellar pneumatization, followed by sellar (53, 26.5%) and presellar (49, 24.5%) types. The conchal type was observed in only (5, 2.5%) patients only. The results are consistent with previous research, where a higher prevalence of the postsellar type is recorded in Pakistan (63.3%) [6], United states of Americans (54%) [7], Turkish (83.5%) [8], Brazilians (63%) [9], Iranian (57.8%) [10], Turkey (62.7%) [11] and Nepalese populations (52%) [12]. Meanwhile, higher prevalence of the sellar type was reported in two separate Nigerian studies [13,14], and Indian [15] populations with percentage of 53.9%, 88.3%, and 55% respectively.

The conchal type of pneumatization was recorded in 5 (2.5%) of patients in our study. The low percentage of conchal type pneumatization in our study agrees with previous studies done by [6] (0.75%), [11] (0.7%), [16] (2.8%), and [17] (1.9%). However, Beryl et al recorded a prevalence of 8.3% in a study done in Delta State, Nigeria. This value is much higher than most seen in the literature. Several other studies did not record any case of conchal type pneumatization [18,19].

The variability in the pattern of pneumatization in our study when compared with other literatures could be attributed to the differences in imaging techniques and ethno-geographical diversity.

Sphenoid sinus absence is a rare developmental anomaly where the sphenoid sinus fails to develop. In the course of this study, we did not come across sphenoid sinus aplasia. This was consistent with the reports by [20] who documented the rarity of this variant [25].

[21] documented a low prevalence of sphenoid sinus aplasia (2.5%) in their study in Turkey. The knowledge of the existence of sphenoid sinus aplasia is important to avoid its misdiagnosis as sinusitis or neoplasm. A non-pneumatized sphenoid sinus may be associated with craniofacial anomalies or skeletal diseases [26].

The study showed no statistically significant association between Age and Sex with Sphenoid Sinus Type ($p > 0.05$). Although in all the SS pneumatization types documented, the male gender accounted for more when compared with the female gender. This could be deduced from the facts that we had analyzed more male brain CT than the female participants (118, 59.0%) vs 82, (41.0%). [11] in Turkey also recorded similar findings where no significant correlation was observed between these qualitative variables and gender.

Conclusion

The postsellar and conchal type of sphenoid sinus pneumatization was found to be the commonest and the least commonest in our environment. Preoperative radiographic evaluation of the anatomical characteristics of sphenoid sinus is essential. Obtaining these images, will provide a safe and accurate transsphenoidal and extended endoscopic skull base approaches.

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Conflict of Interest

None declared.

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